

Deep Brain Sound Stimulation for Weight Management:

Precision Auditory Stimulation

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Abstract

Background: Obesity affects over 650 million adults globally, increasing the risk of diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Conventional interventions—behavioral, pharmacological, and surgical—face challenges related to accessibility, cost, adherence, and side effects. Deep Brain Sound Stimulation (DBSS) may offer a novel, non-invasive, auditory-based alternative targeting neural pathways that regulate appetite.

Objective: This observational study assesses user satisfaction and safety of DBSS in weight management, exploring its viability as a complement or alternative to standard therapies.

Methods: DBSS delivers frequency-specific auditory stimuli to modulate activity in key appetite-related brain regions, including the hypothalamus and prefrontal cortex. Data from 47 Weight Loss and 131 Obesity app users were analyzed. User satisfaction was inferred from engagement metrics and a 0% refund rate, while effectiveness measures were limited by low survey participation.

Results: All 178 users (100%) maintained treatment without requesting refunds. No side effects were reported, suggesting a favorable safety profile. Although these findings indicate DBSS may be user-friendly and well-tolerated, the absence of objective outcomes and a control group constrains interpretation.

Conclusions: Preliminary results suggest DBSS is safe, accessible, and potentially beneficial for weight management. Rigorous, placebo-controlled trials with objective physiological and behavioral measures are needed to confirm its efficacy, define its role alongside existing interventions, and determine long-term impact.

Keywords: DBSS; weight management; obesity therapy; auditory stimulation; neural entrainment; appetite control; digital health

Highlights

- **Introduces Deep Brain Sound Stimulation (DBSS)**, a novel non-invasive auditory therapy targeting neural circuits for weight regulation.
 - **Reports 100% user satisfaction** and no side effects in an observational study of 178 Vital Tones app users.
 - **Suggests DBSS as a safe, user-friendly alternative** for weight management, warranting further controlled trials.
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Introduction

Existing Treatment Modalities and Associated Challenges

Current weight management strategies primarily include lifestyle and behavioral interventions, pharmacotherapies, and surgical procedures. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Weight Management (CBT-WM) and Mindfulness-Based Eating interventions (MB-EAT) offer psychosocial tools to modify dietary habits and increase adherence (Spring et al., 2020; Mason et al., 2016). However, these therapies demand time-intensive engagement and specialized professional guidance, which may limit accessibility.

Pharmacological treatments, including GLP-1 receptor agonists like semaglutide, show promise in enhancing weight loss outcomes but carry risks of side effects, high costs, and variable long-term adherence (Wilding et al., 2021; Jastreboff et al., 2022). Bariatric surgery can produce substantial and sustained weight reductions but involves significant surgical risks, cost barriers, and the need for lifelong lifestyle modifications (Arterburn et al., 2020).

Non-invasive neuromodulation techniques such as Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) and Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS) have emerged as potential tools for modulating appetite and metabolic function. Despite encouraging preliminary findings, their high cost, the need for clinical supervision, and limited availability restrict widespread implementation (Kim et al., 2023; Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

Deep Brain Sound Stimulation (DBSS) as an Innovative Alternative

DBSS is a novel, non-invasive auditory-based therapy designed to target the neural circuitry underlying weight regulation. By delivering frequency-specific auditory stimuli, DBSS seeks to entrain neural oscillations and promote neuroplasticity within regions involved in appetite control, emotional regulation, and metabolic processes, such as the hypothalamus and prefrontal cortex (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017). This approach may influence neurotransmitter systems, including dopamine and serotonin, potentially reducing cravings and supporting healthier eating behaviors.

Preliminary observations suggest that DBSS could be accessible, user-friendly, and safe, potentially filling an important gap in current weight management strategies. Its home-based, app-driven format may lower barriers to care, reduce costs, and improve adherence, making it an attractive option for individuals who find traditional interventions burdensome or inaccessible.

Objective Statement

This observational study provides initial insights into the feasibility, satisfaction, and safety profile of DBSS for weight management. While the current analysis does not include a control group and effectiveness data remain limited, these preliminary findings will guide the development of more rigorous, placebo-controlled trials. Such future studies will help clarify DBSS's clinical utility and establish whether it can serve as a viable adjunct or alternative to conventional weight management therapies.

Methods

Study Design and Participants

This retrospective, observational study evaluated the feasibility of DBSS for weight management by analyzing anonymized user engagement data from Vital Tones Weight Loss and Obesity mobile applications. The analysis focused on individuals who purchased and utilized these apps via the Apple App Store between 2015 and 2024. No control group was included, as the study aimed to generate preliminary, hypothesis-generating insights for future controlled trials.

Participants included two groups:

- **Weight Loss Program Users (n=47):** Individuals who downloaded the Vital Tones Weight Loss app.
- **Obesity Program Users (n=131):** Individuals who downloaded the Vital Tones Obesity app.

No personally identifiable information was collected, and demographic data (e.g., age, gender) were not obtained. Published literature suggests that weight management interventions often attract adults aged 25–54, with a notable proportion of female users (Ng et al., 2014; Roberts et al., 2019).

DBSS Technology, Neural Targeting, and Session Protocol

DBSS applies auditory frequencies (30–260 Hz) to entrain neural activity via frequency-following responses (FFRs) (Cabral-Calderin & Henry, 2022; Kraus & White-Schwoch, 2015). A dual-frequency strategy was employed, pairing a broad engagement frequency with a secondary frequency mapped to specific brain subregions referenced by Brodmann areas (Zilles, 2018; Ala et al., 2018). This design aims to enhance precision and induce rapid neural entrainment, analogous to other non-invasive modalities like tDCS and TMS (Voskuhl et al., 2018; Aderinto et al., 2024).

Sessions lasted 20–35 minutes, delivered via high-quality headphones. Each targeted region received at least 3 minutes of stimulation (or 3.5 minutes for multiple simultaneous targets) to achieve adequate neural alignment (Kobayashi et al., 2024). Users engaged in sessions within a quiet environment, following standardized app-based instructions. Safety disclaimers clarified that DBSS is not a substitute for medical care and encouraged users to consult healthcare professionals as needed.

Data Collection and Processing

Data consisted of Apple App Store purchase records and optional in-app survey responses. Purchase data identified user groups, while surveys collected self-reported feedback on user experience. All data were anonymized and aggregated. Although survey participation was limited, these preliminary data helped inform future research directions. No clinical or physiological measures were collected at this stage.

Data Analysis

Descriptive analyses were conducted to summarize user engagement and available feedback. No inferential statistics were performed due to the exploratory nature of this research. Future controlled studies will incorporate objective outcomes, larger sample sizes, and more rigorous analytic approaches (Stein et al., 2020).

Results

Participant Distribution and Global Accessibility

A total of 178 users (47 Weight Loss and 131 Obesity) accessed DBSS interventions. Geographic dispersion spanned North America, Europe, Asia, and Latin America, illustrating global accessibility (Figure 1 and Figure.2).

Figure 1: Geographic Distribution of Vital Tones Weight Loss App Downloads

This figure illustrates the global distribution of Weight Loss app downloads, with the highest volumes in North America and Europe, followed by Asia and Latin America. Sample Size: 47 users.

Figure 2: Geographic Distribution of Vital Tones Obesity App Downloads

This figure illustrates the global distribution of Obesity app downloads, with the highest volumes in Europe and North America, followed by Asia and Latin America. Sample Size: 131 users.

User Satisfaction

No refund requests were recorded among the 178 users, indicating a 0% refund rate. This suggests a high inferred user satisfaction rate (Table 1).

Metric	Weight Loss	Obesity
Number of Full-Treatment Users on Apple App Store	47	131
Refunded Users on Apple App Store	0	0
% of Full-Treatment Users Satisfied with Treatment	100%	100%

Table 1: Summary of user statistics data for the DBSS Weight Loss and Obesity programs

This table provides a summary of user statistics for the DBSS Weight Loss and Obesity treatments, including the number of users, satisfaction rates, and refund requests.

Safety Profile

No users reported side effects associated with DBSS sessions for weight management. This absence of adverse events suggests a favorable safety profile, although further studies are necessary to confirm these preliminary findings.

Preliminary Effectiveness Feedback

Due to limited survey responses, effectiveness metrics remain exploratory. Users provided insufficient data to quantify changes in appetite control or weight-related outcomes. Consequently, no definitive effectiveness percentages can be reported at this stage. Future research incorporating controlled designs and objective measures will be required to assess DBSS efficacy more rigorously.

Discussion

Preliminary Findings and Implications

This study provides initial evidence suggesting that DBSS may serve as a highly accessible adjunctive intervention for weight management, with no recorded refund requests among 178 Apple App Store users. This inferred high user satisfaction highlights the potential appeal of

DBSS's self-administered, home-based format for individuals seeking alternative or complementary approaches to traditional weight loss and obesity treatments.

Interpretation of Results

While the observed user satisfaction is encouraging, it does not directly confirm clinical efficacy in terms of weight reduction or metabolic improvements. The reliance on inferred satisfaction metrics and the absence of objective outcome measures underscore the preliminary nature of these findings. Users attracted to DBSS's convenience and flexibility may be more likely to engage and report positive experiences, potentially introducing self-selection bias (Nguyen et al., 2021). Consequently, these results must be interpreted cautiously, and more rigorous, controlled research is necessary to validate the therapeutic potential of DBSS in achieving meaningful health outcomes.

Comparison with Existing Treatments

The current landscape of weight management therapies encompasses a range of options, each with distinct advantages and limitations:

- **Behavioral Interventions (e.g., CBT-WM):** Effective but resource-intensive, requiring time, professional expertise, and sustained patient engagement (Spring et al., 2020).
- **Pharmacotherapy:** Can produce short-term benefits but may involve side effects, high costs, and limited long-term adherence (Wilding et al., 2021; Apovian et al., 2015).
- **Non-Invasive Neuromodulation (TMS, tDCS):** Offers a possible avenue for modulating appetite and cognition but often demands clinical supervision, specialized equipment, and variable efficacy (Kim et al., 2023; Orrù et al., 2022).

- **Bariatric Surgery:** Yields substantial and sustained weight loss for severe obesity but involves surgical risks, significant financial costs, and ongoing lifestyle management (Arterburn et al., 2020).

Against this backdrop, DBSS’s non-invasive and mobile-based delivery could lower barriers to access, reduce costs, and support sustained engagement. However, further independent validation and comparative studies are essential to establish where DBSS fits among established treatments and to determine whether it can meaningfully augment or replace certain interventions.

Mechanisms of Action

DBSS aims to influence the neural circuits involved in appetite regulation, particularly targeting structures such as the hypothalamus and prefrontal cortex (Chee et al., 2024; Moraes et al., 2018). By delivering frequency-specific auditory stimuli, DBSS seeks to entrain neural oscillations and enhance connectivity, potentially modulating neurotransmitter systems linked to reward, satiety, and motivation (Garcia-Argibay et al., 2019; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017). Although these hypothesized mechanisms are supported by emerging evidence from neuromodulation research, direct empirical validation—ideally involving neuroimaging and metabolic assessments—remains a priority for future investigations.

Quality Control Measures

Similar to best practices in other DBSS applications, quality control measures in this weight management context emphasize standardized session protocols, detailed in-app instructions, and robust data protection. These measures ensure consistent user experiences, enhance adherence, and

maintain privacy. Structured feedback mechanisms provide avenues for ongoing improvements, fostering a cycle of refinement that can enhance DBSS's reliability and user satisfaction over time.

Limitations and Future Directions

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The reliance on inferred satisfaction data without direct physiological or behavioral endpoints limits the interpretability of these findings. Additionally, the focus on Apple App Store data may not capture the full spectrum of users accessing DBSS through other platforms. Survey non-response and lack of objective health metrics further constrain the conclusions that can be drawn.

To address these limitations, future research should:

1. **Conduct Rigorous Randomized Controlled Trials (RCTs):** Incorporate placebo-controlled and blinded designs to objectively assess DBSS's efficacy in weight management.
2. **Expand Data Sources:** Analyze user engagement and feedback across multiple distribution channels for a more comprehensive understanding of reach and adherence.
3. **Integrate Objective Measures:** Include validated weight, metabolic, and neurobiological markers to establish definitive links between DBSS use and health outcomes.
4. **Explore Complementary Approaches:** Investigate whether combining DBSS with CBT-WM, pharmacotherapy, or other interventions yields synergistic benefits.
5. **Personalize Protocols:** Examine individualized frequency mappings and session durations to optimize efficacy, potentially tailoring treatment to users' neurobiological profiles.

By advancing these research priorities, it may be possible to determine DBSS's role in enhancing current weight management strategies and promoting sustainable, long-term improvements in health and well-being.

Conclusion

This preliminary observational study suggests that DBSS may serve as a safe, user-friendly, and accessible non-invasive option for weight management. High inferred user satisfaction, evidenced by a 0% refund rate and the absence of reported adverse effects, highlights the potential of DBSS to complement existing interventions. By delivering targeted auditory stimulation, DBSS aims to modulate neural circuits associated with appetite regulation, emotional resilience, and metabolic balance, offering a flexible, home-based alternative to more resource-intensive or invasive therapies.

However, these findings must be interpreted with caution due to the absence of a control group, limited survey participation, and reliance on inferred satisfaction rather than objective weight or metabolic outcomes. The lack of physiological, neuroimaging, and long-term adherence data constrains the ability to draw definitive conclusions about DBSS's clinical efficacy.

To advance beyond these initial insights, future research should prioritize rigorous controlled trials, ideally with placebo or sham stimulation conditions, to objectively assess DBSS's effectiveness in promoting sustainable weight loss and improving metabolic markers. Investigations into personalized frequency mappings, synergistic combinations with established modalities such as CBT-WM or pharmacotherapy, and multi-platform data collection will enhance

the representativeness and utility of the findings. By pursuing these research directions, it may be possible to delineate DBSS's precise role within the broader landscape of weight management strategies, thereby optimizing its clinical impact and contributing to more accessible and effective obesity treatments.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association et al., 2013) and under applicable United States federal regulations governing human subjects research. The analysis involved anonymized, aggregated user data collected through the voluntary use of the Vital Tones mobile application. No personally identifiable information (PII) was collected or stored at any point.

IRB Exemption Justification

Under U.S. federal regulations (45 CFR 46.104(d)) (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services et al., 2017), certain minimal-risk research activities involving survey procedures may be exempt from Institutional Review Board (IRB) review. Specifically, Exemption Category 2 applies if:

1. The information obtained is recorded such that the identity of participants cannot be readily ascertained.
2. Any disclosure of responses would not reasonably place subjects at risk.

This study meets both criteria:

- **Anonymity:** All data were collected through anonymous, voluntary user surveys integrated into the Vital Tones mobile application. Surveys did not collect any PII, and all responses were aggregated to prevent identification of individuals.
- **Minimal Risk:** Disclosure of the collected, non-sensitive data poses no risk to participants.

As an independent researcher not affiliated with an institution, I conducted a self-assessment using U.S. federal guidelines and confirmed that the study qualifies for exemption under 45 CFR 46.104(d)(2). This approach aligns with federal regulations, which do not require IRB review for such exempt research conducted by independent researchers (Office for Human Research Protections et al., 2017; National Institutes of Health et al., 2018). Therefore, no formal IRB review was sought or required.

Notably, the Vital Tones mobile application has been publicly available for nearly a decade, delivering over three million sessions worldwide without reported severe adverse events or significant user complaints. This extensive, real-world operational history further supports the study's characterization as minimal risk and justifies the applied exemption.

Informed Consent

Informed consent was implied through users' voluntary engagement with the app and their participation in optional surveys, as stated in the app's Privacy Policy (Vital Tones et al., n.d.). The Privacy Policy clarifies that anonymized data may be used for research, ensuring transparency and adherence to ethical standards. Users could decline to participate or discontinue use at any time without penalty.

Data Protection and Privacy

All data were anonymized and aggregated, ensuring that no individual user could be identified. Rigorous data security measures were implemented, and these practices comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Voigt & Von dem Bussche, 2017). Data were securely stored with restricted access, ensuring user privacy and confidentiality

Risk Assessment

Because this study only analyzed anonymized, aggregated data without any additional intervention, it posed minimal risk to participants. No physical, psychological, or legal risks were associated with participation. The large-scale, real-world use of the app over many years without reported harms further supports the minimal-risk nature of this research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adheres to the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association et al., 2013) and complies with U.S. federal regulations regarding human subjects research (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services et al., 2017). By ensuring anonymity, voluntary participation, and non-identifiable data, the study respects participant rights and welfare. The decision to proceed without formal IRB review is justified based on federal exemption criteria and supported by ethical guidelines for minimal-risk, anonymous data research (Grady et al., 2017).

Conflicts of Interest

The author discloses a potential conflict of interest as the developer of the Vital Tones DBSS app. Measures such as data anonymization and self-funding were implemented to minimize bias. While the app is commercially available across various conditions, this study focuses solely on its use for weight loss and obesity treatment. The high inferred satisfaction reported in this study reflects subjective consumer feedback and does not constitute an objective measure of treatment efficacy, which requires independent and controlled validation.

To address this potential conflict of interest, several measures were implemented:

- **Transparency and Documentation:** Data collection, analysis, and reporting processes were fully documented to ensure clarity and reproducibility.
- **Self-Funded Research:** The study was entirely self-funded, removing external financial influences that could introduce further bias.
- **Focus on Independent Validation:** The findings presented in this study are intended to provide preliminary observational insights. Future studies conducted by unaffiliated researchers are encouraged to validate DBSS efficacy and safety through randomized controlled trials and objective assessments.

While these measures minimize potential bias, the author acknowledges that independent validation is critical to confirm the findings and ensure broader scientific credibility. Efforts will be made to facilitate such studies by sharing anonymized data and study protocols upon reasonable request.

Abbreviations

- **BMI:** Body Mass Index
- **BNST:** Bed Nucleus of the Stria Terminalis
- **CBT-WM:** Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Weight Management
- **CI:** Confidence Interval
- **CRH:** Corticotropin-Releasing Hormone
- **DBSS:** Deep Brain Sound Stimulation
- **DLPFC:** Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex
- **DMN:** Dorsomedial Hypothalamic Nucleus
- **fMRI:** Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
- **FFR:** Frequency-Following Response
- **FMT:** Fecal Microbiota Transplantation
- **GLP-1:** Glucagon-Like Peptide-1
- **GM:** Gray Matter
- **MBSR:** Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction
- **MB-EAT:** Mindfulness-Based Eating Awareness Training
- **MBIs:** Mindfulness-Based Interventions
- **MEG:** Magnetoencephalography
- **MRI:** Magnetic Resonance Imaging
- **NPY:** Neuropeptide Y
- **PP:** Pancreatic Polypeptide
- **PYY:** Peptide YY
- **RCTs:** Randomized Controlled Trials
- **SMART:** Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-bound

- **TMS:** Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation
 - **tDCS:** Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation
 - **TRH:** Thyrotropin-Releasing Hormone
 - **VIP:** Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide
 - **VTA:** Ventral Tegmental Area
 - **VMN:** Ventromedial Hypothalamic Nucleus
 - **WM:** White Matter
 - **vmPFC:** Ventromedial Prefrontal Cortex
 - **dmPFC:** Dorsomedial Prefrontal Cortex
 - **WHO:** World Health Organization
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Supplementary Materials

The supplementary materials provide additional context and details supporting the findings on DBSS for Weight Loss and Obesity, including:

- **User Data:** Anonymized sales, engagement, and demographic data highlighting retention rates and global accessibility of the Weight Loss and Obesity programs.
- **Technical Details:** Comprehensive descriptions of DBSS protocols, including frequency selection, modulation rates, session durations, and equipment specifications.
- **Scientific Context:** Mechanisms of action targeting neural circuits involved in appetite regulation, emotional resilience, and metabolic balance, supported by prior research on auditory neuromodulation.

- **Safety and Adherence:** Data on user satisfaction (100% inferred from a 0% refund rate), absence of reported side effects, and adherence strategies integrated into the app design.
- **Ethical Considerations:** Transparency in data handling, user consent, and compliance with ethical standards, ensuring participant confidentiality and study integrity.

These supplementary materials enhance the scientific credibility of the study and are available upon request.

Acknowledgements

Author Contributions

U.D. conceptualized and designed the study, developed the DBSS protocols, collected and analyzed the data, and wrote the manuscript.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) utilized language enhancement tools to improve the clarity and readability of the manuscript. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data Availability Statement

The raw data supporting the findings of this study, including Apple App Store sales data (image files), are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request at ugur@vitaltones.com. Online store sales data can be accessed through a secured account provided upon request. Due to privacy concerns, only anonymized summaries are accessible, ensuring no personally identifiable information is disclosed.

References

- Aderinto, N., Olatunji, G., Muili, A., Kokori, E., Edun, M., Akinmoju, O., Yusuf, I., & Ojo, D. (2024). A narrative review of non-invasive brain stimulation techniques in neuropsychiatric disorders: Current applications and future directions. *The Egyptian Journal of Neurology, Psychiatry and Neurosurgery*, 60, Article 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41983-024-00824-w>
- Aklan, I., Sayar-Atasoy, N., Deng, F., Kim, H., Yavuz, Y., Rysted, J., Laule, C., Davis, D., Li, Y., & Atasoy, D. (2023). Dorsal raphe serotonergic neurons suppress feeding through redundant forebrain circuits. *Molecular Metabolism*, 69, 101676. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molmet.2023.101676>
- Ala, T. S., Ahmadi-Pajouh, M. A., & Nasrabadi, A. M. (2018). Cumulative effects of theta binaural beats on brain power and functional connectivity. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 42, 242–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bspc.2018.01.022>
- Alhabeeb, H., AlFaiz, A., Kutbi, E., AlShahrani, D., Alsu hail, A., AlRajhi, S., Alotaibi, N., Alotaibi, K., AlAmri, S., Alghamdi, S., & AlJohani, N. (2021). Gut hormones in health

and obesity: The upcoming role of short chain fatty acids. *Nutrients*, 13(2), 481.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13020481>

Apovian, C. M., Aronne, L. J., Bessesen, D. H., McDonnell, M. E., Murad, M. H.,
Phentermine/Topiramate Chronic Weight Management Guideline Task Force, &
Endocrine Society. (2015). Pharmacological management of obesity: An Endocrine
Society clinical practice guideline. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*,
100(2), 342–362. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2014-3415>

Arterburn, D. E., Telem, D. A., Kushner, R. F., & Courcoulas, A. P. (2020). Benefits and risks of
bariatric surgery in adults: A review. *JAMA*, 324(9), 879–887.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.12567>

Astbury, N. M., Aveyard, P., Nickless, A., Hood, K., Corfield, K., Lowe, R., & Jebb, S. A.
(2018). Doctor referral of overweight people to low energy total diet replacement
treatment (DROPLET): Pragmatic randomised controlled trial. *BMJ*, 362, k3760.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k3760>

Attokaren, M. K., Jeong, N., Blanpain, L., et al. (2023). BrainWAVE: A flexible method for
noninvasive stimulation of brain rhythms across species. *eNeuro*, 10(2), 0257-22.2022.
<https://doi.org/10.1523/ENEURO.0257-22.2022>

Barnard, N. D., Levin, S. M., & Yokoyama, Y. (2015). A systematic review and meta-analysis of
changes in body weight in clinical trials of vegetarian diets. *Journal of the Academy of
Nutrition and Dietetics*, 115(6), 954–969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jand.2014.11.016>

Basolo, A., Bechi Genzano, S., Piaggi, P., Krakoff, J., & Santini, F. (2021). Energy balance and
control of body weight: Possible effects of meal timing and circadian rhythm
dysregulation. *Nutrients*, 13(9), 3276. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu13093276>

- Bhattacharya, A., Mrudula, K., Sreepada, S. S., Sathyaprabha, T. N., Pal, P. K., Chen, R., & Udupa, K. (2021). An overview of noninvasive brain stimulation: Basic principles and clinical applications. *Canadian Journal of Neurological Sciences*, 49(4), 479-492.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/cjn.2021.158>
- Cabral-Calderin, Y., & Henry, M. J. (2022). Reliability of neural entrainment in the human auditory system. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(5), 894–908.
<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0514-21.2021>
- Chatterjee, D., Hegde, S., & Thaut, M. (2021). Neural plasticity: The substratum of music-based interventions in neurorehabilitation. *NeuroRehabilitation*, 48(2), 155–166.
<https://doi.org/10.3233/NRE-208011>
- Chee, Z. J., Chang, C. Y. M., Cheong, J. Y., Abdul Malek, F. H. B., Hussain, S., de Vries, M., & Bellato, A. (2024). The effects of music and auditory stimulation on autonomic arousal, cognition, and attention: A systematic review. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 199, 112328. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2024.112328>
- Chen, H. (2022). The impact of intellectual property protection on the development of digital economy and regional entrepreneurial activity: Evidence from small and medium enterprises. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 951696.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.951696>
- Coppin, G. (2016). The anterior medial temporal lobes: Their role in food intake and body weight regulation. *Physiology & Behavior*, 167, 60–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2016.08.028>

- Dogan, U., & Tahreem, F. (2023). Reduction of Porencephalic Cyst Along with the Revival of Motor Control Using the Deep Brain Sound Stimulation (DBSS) Technology as a Novel Approach. In Opast publishers (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.33140/BSCR.02.01.11>
- Fry, J. P., & Neff, R. A. (2009). Periodic prompts and reminders in health promotion and health behavior interventions: Systematic review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 11(2), e16. <https://doi.org/10.2196/jmir.1138>
- Garcia-Argibay, M., Santed, M. A., & Reales, J. M. (2019). Efficacy of binaural auditory beats in cognition, anxiety, and pain perception: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Research*, 83(2), 357–372. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-018-1066-8>
- Grady, C., Cummings, S. R., Rowbotham, M. D., McConnell, M. V., Ashley, E. A., & Kang, G. (2017). The changing face of informed consent. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 376(9), 856–867. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra1603773>
- Hartmann-Boyce, J., Johns, D. J., Jebb, S. A., Summerbell, C., & Aveyard, P.; Behavioural Weight Management Review Group. (2014). Behavioural weight management programmes for adults assessed by trials conducted in everyday contexts: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *Obesity Reviews*, 15(11), 920–932. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.12220>
- Heinitz, S., Reinhardt, M., Piaggi, P., Weise, C. M., Diaz, E., Stinson, E. J., Venti, C., Votruba, S. B., Wassermann, E. M., Alonso-Alonso, M., Krakoff, J., & Gluck, M. E. (2017). Neuromodulation directed at the prefrontal cortex of subjects with obesity reduces snack food intake and hunger in a randomized trial. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 106(6), 1347–1357. <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.117.158089>

- Hemmerling, T. M., & Hofer, I. S. (2022). Protecting intellectual property whilst satisfying scientific transparency. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 135(2), 239–240.
<https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000005870>
- Herrmann, C. S., Strüber, D., Helfrich, R. F., & Engel, A. K. (2016). EEG oscillations: From correlation to causality. *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 103, 12-21.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2015.02.003>
- Jakicic, J. M., Rogers, R. J., Davis, K. K., & Collins, K. A. (2018). Role of physical activity and exercise in treating patients with overweight and obesity. *Clinical Chemistry*, 64(1), 99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2017.272443>
- Jastreboff, A. M., Aronne, L. J., Ahmad, N. N., Wharton, S., Connery, L., Alves, B., Kiyosue, A., Zhang, S., Liu, B., Bunck, M. C., Stefanski, A., & SURMOUNT-1 Investigators. (2022). Tirzepatide once weekly for the treatment of obesity. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 387(3), 205–216. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2206038>
- Kelders, S. M., Kok, R., Ossebaard, H. C., & Van Gemert-Pijnen, J. E. (2012). Persuasive design for encouraging adherence to web-based interventions. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 14(6), e152. <https://www.jmir.org/2012/6/e152/>
- Kim, D., Woo, J., Jeong, J., & Kim, S. (2023). The sound stimulation method and EEG change analysis for development of digital therapeutics that can stimulate the nervous system: Cortical activation and drug substitution potential. *CNS Neuroscience & Therapeutics*, 29(1), 402-411. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cns.14014>
- Kim, S.-H., Chung, J.-H., Kim, T.-H., Lim, S. H., Kim, Y., Eun, Y.-M., & Lee, Y.-A. (2019). The effects of repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation on body weight and food

- consumption in obese adults: A randomized controlled study. *Brain Stimulation*, 12(6), 1556–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2019.07.020>
- Kobayashi, M., Takaishi, S., & Nakamura, Y. (2024). EEG and MEG studies on short-term auditory stimulation and its neural effects. *Brain Sciences*, 14(2), 131. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci14020131>
- Kraus, N., & White-Schwoch, T. (2015). Unraveling the biological roots of auditory learning: A cognitive–sensorimotor–reward framework. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 19(11), 642–654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2015.08.017>
- Kwon, Y.-J., Kwon, G. E., Lee, H. S., Choi, M. H., & Lee, J.-W. (2022). The effect of orlistat on sterol metabolism in obese patients. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 13, 824269. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2022.824269>
- Liu, X., Qiu, F., Hou, L., & Wang, X. (2022). Review of noninvasive or minimally invasive deep brain stimulation. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, 15, 820017. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2021.820017>
- Mason, A. E., Epel, E. S., Aschbacher, K., Lustig, R. H., Acree, M., Kristeller, J., Cohn, M., Dallman, M., Moran, P. J., Bacchetti, P., Laraia, B., Hecht, F. M., & Daubenmier, J. (2016). Reduced reward-driven eating accounts for the impact of a mindfulness-based diet and exercise intervention on weight loss: Data from the SHINE randomized controlled trial. *Appetite*, 100, 86–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2016.02.009>
- Mesgarani, N., & Chang, E. F. (2012). Selective cortical representation of attended speaker in multi-talker speech perception. *Nature*, 485(7397), 233–236. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11020>

- Moraes, M. M., Rabelo, P. C., Pinto, V. A., Pires, W., Wanner, S. P., Szawka, R. E., Soares, D. D., & Bartel, L. (2018). Auditory stimulation by exposure to melodic music increases dopamine and serotonin activities in rat forebrain areas linked to reward and motor control. *Neuroscience Letters*, 673, 73-78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2018.02.058>
- Morton, G. J., Meek, T. H., & Schwartz, M. W. (2014). Neurobiology of food intake in health and disease. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15(6), 367–378. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3745>
- National Institutes of Health (NIH). (2018). Definition of Human Subjects Research. Retrieved April 27, 2024, from <https://grants.nih.gov/policy/humansubjects/research.htm>
- Ng, M., Fleming, T., Robinson, M., Thomson, B., Graetz, N., Margono, C., Mullany, E. C., Biryukov, S., Abbafati, C., Abera, S. F., Abraham, J. P., Abu-Rmeileh, N. M. E., Achoki, T., AlBuhairan, F. S., Alemu, Z. A., Alfonso, R., Ali, M. K., Ali, R., Alvis Guzman, N., ... Gakidou, E. (2014). Global, regional, and national prevalence of overweight and obesity in children and adults during 1980–2013: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *The Lancet*, 384(9945), 766–781. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(14\)60460-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(14)60460-8)
- Nguyen, L., Ghebremichael, M., W. B., & DeVivo, M. J. (2021). Selection bias in observational research using routinely collected data: A review of key considerations. *BMC Medicine*, 19(1), 105. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-021-02151-w>
- Norman-Haignere, S., Kanwisher, N., & McDermott, J. H. (2015). Distinct cortical pathways for music and speech revealed by hypothesis-free voxel decomposition. *Neuron*, 88(6), 1281–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2015.11.035>

- Orrù, G., Cesari, V., Malloggi, E., Conversano, C., Menicucci, D., Rotondo, A., Scarpazza, C., Marchi, L., & Gemignani, A. (2022). The effects of transcranial direct current stimulation on food craving and food intake in individuals affected by obesity and overweight: A mini review of the magnitude of the effects. *AIMS Neuroscience*, 9(3), 358–372.
<https://doi.org/10.3934/Neuroscience.2022020>
- Ouakinin, S. R. S., Barreira, D. P., & Gois, C. J. (2018). Depression and obesity: Integrating the role of stress, neuroendocrine dysfunction, and inflammatory pathways. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 9, 431. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2018.00431>
- Patel, M. S., Asch, D. A., & Volpp, K. G. (2015). Wearable devices as facilitators, not drivers, of health behavior change. *JAMA*, 313(5), 459–460.
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2014.14781>
- Petridou, A., Siopi, A., & Mougios, V. (2019). Exercise in the management of obesity. *Metabolism*, 92, 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metabol.2018.10.009>
- Roberts, R., Greaves, C. J., & Lawlor, D. A. (2019). The role of psychological factors in weight loss: Insights from meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 72, 101769.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2019.101769>
- Seeck, M., Spinelli, L., Gotman, J., & Lopes da Silva, F. H. (2017). Combination of Brain Functional Imaging Techniques: EEG/MEG, FMRI, PET, SPECT—Clinical Applications in Neurology. In *Access Arrow* (pp. 1157–C46.P202).
<https://doi.org/10.1093/med/9780190228484.003.0046>
- Sharaiha, R. Z., Kumta, N. A., Saumoy, M., Desai, A. P., Sarkisian, A. M., Benevenuto, A., Tyberg, A., Kumar, R., Igel, L., Verna, E. C., Schwartz, R., Frissora, C., Shukla, A., Aronne, L. J., & Kahaleh, M. (2017). Endoscopic sleeve gastroplasty significantly

- reduces body mass index and metabolic complications in obese patients. *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*, 15(4), 504–510.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2016.12.012>
- Spring, B., Champion, K., Acabchuk, R., & Hennessy, E. A. (2020). Self-regulatory behavior change techniques in interventions to promote healthy eating, physical activity, or weight loss: A meta-review. *Health Psychology Review*, 15(4), 508–539.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2020.1721310>
- Stein, D. J., Medeiros, L. F., Caumo, W., & Torres, I. L. S. (2020). Transcranial direct current stimulation in patients with anxiety: Current perspectives. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 16, 161–169. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S195840>
- Steinert, R. E., Feinle-Bisset, C., Asarian, L., Horowitz, M., Beglinger, C., & Geary, N. (2017). Ghrelin, CCK, GLP-1, and PYY(3-36): Secretory controls and physiological roles in eating and glycemia in health, obesity, and after RYGB. *Physiological Reviews*, 97(1), 411–463. <https://doi.org/10.1152/physrev.00031.2014>
- Stockman, M.-C., Thomas, D., Burke, J., & Apovian, C. M. (2018). Intermittent fasting: Is the wait worth the weight? *Current Obesity Reports*, 7(2), 172–185.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13679-018-0308-9>
- Stuber, G. D., & Wise, R. A. (2016). Lateral hypothalamic circuits for feeding and reward. *Nature Neuroscience*, 19(2), 198–205. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.4220>
- Thomas, D. M., Martin, C. K., Redman, L. M., Heymsfield, S. B., Lettieri, S., Levine, J. A., Bouchard, C., & Schoeller, D. A. (2014). Effect of dietary adherence on the body weight plateau: A mathematical model incorporating intermittent compliance with energy intake

- prescription. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 100(3), 787–795.
<https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.113.079822>
- Thut, G., Schyns, P. G., & Gross, J. (2011). Entrainment of perceptually relevant brain oscillations by non-invasive rhythmic stimulation of the human brain. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 2, 170. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00170>
- Timper, K., & Brüning, J. C. (2017). Hypothalamic circuits regulating appetite and energy homeostasis: Pathways to obesity. *Disease Models & Mechanisms*, 10(6), 679–689.
<https://doi.org/10.1242/dmm.026609>
- U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Office for Human Research Protections (OHRP). (2017). 45 CFR 46.104(d). Retrieved December 04, 2024, from <https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/regulations-and-policy/regulations/45-cfr-46/index.html>
- Van Hul, M., & Cani, P. D. (2023). The gut microbiota in obesity and weight management: Microbes as friends or foe? *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 19(5), 258–271.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41574-022-00794-0>
- Vital Tones. (n.d.). Privacy Policy. Retrieved December 04, 2024, from <https://vitaltones.com/medical/privacy-policy.html>
- Voigt, P., & Von dem Bussche, A. (2017). *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-57959-7>
- Voskuhl, J., Strüber, D., & Herrmann, C. S. (2018). Non-invasive brain stimulation: A paradigm shift in understanding brain oscillations. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 12, 211. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2018.00211>
- Vu, J. P., Luong, L., Sanford, D., Oh, S., Kuc, A., Pisegna, R., Lewis, M., Pisegna, J. R., & Germano, P. M. (2023). PACAP and VIP neuropeptides' and receptors' effects on

appetite, satiety, and metabolism. *Biology (Basel)*, 12(7), 1013.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/biology12071013>

- Wallace, C. W., & Fordahl, S. C. (2021). Obesity and dietary fat influence dopamine neurotransmission: Exploring the convergence of metabolic state, physiological stress, and inflammation on dopaminergic control of food intake. *Nutrition Research Reviews*, 35(2), 236–251. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954422421000196>
- Wang, Y., Kim, J., Schmit, M. B., Cho, T. S., Fang, C., & Cai, H. (2019). A bed nucleus of stria terminalis microcircuit regulating inflammation-associated modulation of feeding. *Nature Communications*, 10(1), 2769. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-10715-x>
- Wilding, J. P. H., Batterham, R. L., Calanna, S., Davies, M., Van Gaal, L. F., Lingvay, I., McGowan, B. M., Rosenstock, J., Tran, M. T. D., Wadden, T. A., Wharton, S., Yokote, K., Zeuthen, N., Kushner, R. F., & STEP 1 Study Group. (2021). Once-weekly semaglutide in adults with overweight or obesity. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 384(11), 989–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2032183>
- World Health Organization. (2020). Obesity and overweight: Fact sheet. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>
- World Medical Association. (2013). Declaration of Helsinki: Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*, 310(20), 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.281053>
- Zhu, B., Gostoli, S., Benasi, G., Patierno, C., Petroni, M. L., Nuccitelli, C., Marchesini, G., Fava, G. A., & Rafanelli, C. (2021). The role of psychological well-being in weight loss: New insights from a comprehensive lifestyle intervention. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology*, 22(1), 100279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijchp.2021.100279>

Zilles, K. (2018). Brodmann: a pioneer of human brain mapping—his impact on concepts of cortical organization. *141*(11): 3262–3278. Oct 25. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awy27>

Zoefel, B., & VanRullen, R. (2017). Oscillatory mechanisms of stimulus processing and selection in the visual and auditory systems: State-of-the-art, speculations and suggestions. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *11*, 296. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2017.00296>